

Proton Energy Dependence of SiC Power MOSFET Single-Event Burnout Sensitivity

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Abstract—The proton energy dependence of single-event burnout (SEB) sensitivity of silicon carbide (SiC) power MOSFETs is studied. The experimental results show that SEB is dependent on the primary proton energy and the drain bias voltage applied during irradiation. The secondary particles, produced by the nuclear reactions between primary particles and device materials, are studied using Geant4 simulations. A method for finding the criteria for the failure based on experimental radiation data and Geant4 simulation data is presented.

Index Terms—Power MOSFET, proton irradiation, silicon carbide (SiC), single-event burnout (SEB).

I. INTRODUCTION

SILICON carbide (SiC) has gained considerable interest in the field of power electronics applications, due to its superior material properties when compared to silicon. SiC is a wide-bandgap (WBG) material, characterized by a high critical electric field, high thermal conductivity, and a high melting point. These properties are advantageous in applications requiring high power density [1], [2]. For instance, the space industry would benefit significantly from the adoption of WBG components in technologies such as electric propulsion and power conditioning units [3]. Furthermore, the automotive industry is rapidly transitioning from combustion engines to fully electric vehicles (EVs), where high energy efficiency can be achieved through the use of WBG technologies [4]. However, the wider adoption of these technologies is still constrained by radiation-induced reliability issues. It has been found that SiC power devices

are sensitive to destructive single-event effects due to radiation impact on space and atmospheric environments [5], [6], [7], [8]. The radiation-induced failure mechanisms of SiC power devices have been under active investigation [6], [9], [10], [11], [12], [13], [14], [15], but are still not fully understood.

While being light particles, protons and neutrons do not generate a sufficient amount of charge by direct ionization to induce device failure. However, the secondary particles created during interactions between the primary particle and the nuclei in target materials can induce significant energy deposition events in the device, and, therefore, result in a catastrophic failure of the power electronics component [16] including SiC power devices [17], [18], [19], [20]. Commonly the production and the transport of the secondary particles within the target structures are investigated through Monte Carlo simulations. Particle type, penetration range, and deposited energy and/or linear energy transfer (LET) of the secondaries are typically considered as the key parameters [13], [17], [20], [21], [22], [23]. On top of the catastrophic failures, parameter degradation, such as leakage current increase, and early failures in time-dependent dielectric breakdown (TDDDB) experiments have been reported for devices under neutron and proton exposures [7], [20].

The proton energies in Earth's orbits range from hundreds of keV up to hundreds of MeV [24]. A single high-energy proton strike can induce a catastrophic failure in the power device. Therefore, the device failure dependence on proton energy needs to be properly assessed. Akturk et al. [25] have reported energy dependence on the neutron-induced single-event burnout (SEB) cross section for SiC power MOSFETs. They found that the SEB cross section reaches its maximum at 50–100-MeV neutron energy range. Proton energy dependence on SiC power device SEB cross section has also been reported for primary proton energies from 30 to 100 MeV, with spallation reaction products responsible for device failure [17], [21].

In this work, we investigate the effect of the proton energy on the SEB sensitivity of SiC power MOSFETs by 101- and 200-MeV proton beams. The mechanisms of secondary particle production and device physics are investigated through Geant4 simulations. A method for estimating the failure criteria based on the experimental results and simulation is proposed.

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Fig. 1. Fluence for each SEB failure in Weibull scale for devices irradiated at $V_{DS} = 1000$ V. The data for 53-MeV protons is from our previous work [20].

II. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

The devices under test (DUTs) are commercial 4H-SiC power MOSFETs manufactured by Wolfspeed (part number C3M0350120D, $V_{DS,max} = 1200$ V). Proton irradiations were performed at the Proton Irradiation Facility (PIF) at the Paul Scherrer Institute, Switzerland. The 101- and 200-MeV proton beams were used. The 101-MeV beam was made by adding an energy degrader to the 200-MeV primary beam. During irradiations, the devices were connected in parallel, and ten DUTs per bias condition and primary proton energy (E_p) were used. The gate-to-source voltage (V_{GS}) was set to 0 V and drain-to-source voltages (V_{DS}) of 400, 500, 600, 700, 800, 900, and 1000 V were applied on the devices, and the total current was monitored with a Keithley 2470 source measure unit (SMU). DUTs were irradiated with proton beam flux of 10^8 $\text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ up to 10^{11} cm^{-2} total fluence. The flux was considered to be constant within 10% uncertainty among the runs and over the DUT area. All the devices were electrically characterized before and after irradiation.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. SEB Experiments

To determine the proton-induced SEB sensitivity, the DUTs were exposed to the proton beam while the total current of the parallel connected devices was monitored. Each DUT failure was detected as an increase in the measured current. The proton fluence for each failure was recorded and for those fluence values, we applied the two-parameter Weibull cumulative distribution function (cdf). The method is described in more detail in [20]. The proton-induced SEB failures are presented in the Weibull scale in Fig. 1. From the extracted fitting parameters, an SEB cross section σ was calculated after the following equation:

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{\eta} \quad (1)$$

where η is the parameter representing fluence when 63% of the population has failed. This value is obtained from the data fit. The resulting cross sections are presented as a function

Fig. 2. Proton energy dependence on the SEB cross section σ . Ten DUTs per primary proton energy configuration were used. The data for 53-MeV protons is from our previous work [20].

Fig. 3. Irradiation drain voltage dependence on the SEB cross section. Ten DUTs per voltage configuration were used. The relatively large uncertainty at $V_{DS} = 700$ V results from only two observed SEBs until the goal fluence was reached.

of primary proton energy in Fig. 2, and also as a function of applied drain voltage in Fig. 3.

As seen in Fig. 2, the increase in proton energy from 101 to 200 MeV increases the SEB cross section at $V_{DS} = 900$ and 1000 V by a factor of 3 and 6, respectively. Moreover, at $V_{DS} = 1000$ V, the SEB cross section for 200-MeV protons is approximately one order of magnitude higher compared to that for 53-MeV protons reported in [20].

The increase in cross section with increasing primary particle energy can be attributed to the higher probability of primary protons producing secondary particles with enough range and deposited energy to induce burnout. The secondary particles are discussed in more detail in Section III-C. Interestingly, the SEB cross section value for 200-MeV protons is in close agreement with atmospheric neutron induced-SEB cross section values for similar devices [7], [25].

In comparison with heavy-ion results, the SEB sensitivity is strongly dependent on the LET when $\text{LET} < 10$ $\text{MeV cm}^2 \text{mg}^{-1}$. Above that LET value, the SEB voltage threshold saturates around 500 V [6]. In our experiments, we did not observe SEB below $V_{DS} = 700$ V.

Moreover, strong drain voltage dependence on the SEB cross section is observed in Fig. 3. This suggests that most of the secondary particles causing the SEB have LET around $10 \text{ MeV cm}^2 \text{ mg}^{-1}$ and below.

B. Degradation of the Survived Devices

Concerning their functional parameters, the devices that did not exhibit SEB during the irradiation experiment maintained their blocking and switching capabilities. However, the current versus voltage characterizations for some of the irradiated devices show leakage current degradation. For a device irradiated at $V_{DS} = 800 \text{ V}$, I - V characterizations are presented in Fig. 4. Even though no major changes were observed in transfer characteristics [see Fig. 4(a)], it should be noted that the gate leakage current shows strong increase, observed through both drain voltage [see Fig. 4(b)] and gate voltage [see Fig. 4(c)] sweeps. Similar gate degradation has been previously reported for devices exposed to atmospheric neutrons [7]. As shown in Fig. 4(b), the drain leakage current exhibits two orders of magnitude increase for the irradiated device, and the leakage is dominated by the drain-to-gate current. This drain-to-gate current path has been previously reported for heavy-ion irradiated MOSFETs [14], [15]. However, the leakage reported here is less severe and occurs at higher V_{DS} compared to that from heavy ions. Also, it is unclear whether the degradation is due to a single proton interaction which would indicate a single-event leakage current (SELC) type of degradation, or if it has a cumulative nature, requiring an accumulation of defects to be observed.

The gate current during the gate voltage sweep shows a strong leakage current degradation [see Fig. 4(c)], reaching 1 nA at around $V_{GS} = 12 \text{ V}$. Such leakage might have an impact on the efficient switching operation of the SiC MOSFET causing increased power consumption in the power converter. The leakage currents for this device are still within the datasheet limits but it raises a concern about the long-term reliability of the device, even if it did not fail during the SEB testing. As an assumption, secondary ions generated by the primary proton interaction have generated free charges in the semiconductor volume. Transport of these charges under an applied electric field has led to localized stress and latent damage sites within the gate oxide which has weakened the device. Such observation highlights the importance of the careful postirradiation characterization of the devices regarding the assessment of the overall reliability in the radiation environments.

In [20], the 53-MeV proton-induced latent gate damage was revealed only through the constant voltage stress (CVS) above the rated gate voltages. Some devices exhibited early failures under CVS but none of them showed any leakage during the postirradiation I - V characterizations. As seen here, with higher proton energies and with the same proton fluence as in [20], we see some leakage current increase for irradiated devices. It seems that in addition to the SEB cross section dependence on proton energy, the latent damage and leakage current degradation is also affected by the primary proton energy.

Fig. 4. Postirradiation characterizations of the device which did not exhibit SEB during irradiation. The device was irradiated at $V_{DS} = 800 \text{ V}$. (a) $I_D - V_{GS}$ characteristics, (b) $I_G - V_{DS}$ and $I_D - V_{DS}$ characteristics, and (c) $I_G - V_{GS}$ characteristics of the device which did not exhibit SEB during irradiation. The device was irradiated at $V_{DS} = 800 \text{ V}$.

C. Simulation Results

When a primary proton hits the device, it can induce nuclear reactions. The reaction products will travel inside the device volume and ionize the material along their tracks and further cause device failure, similar to a failure caused by heavy-ion impact. Regarding the heavy-ion impact, the voltage threshold for SiC power device SEB as a func-

Fig. 5. Characteristics for the secondary particles that satisfy the SEB criteria in the G4SEE simulation. The secondaries which are included in the analysis are indicated in dark red and the excluded secondaries are marked in light gray.

tion of LET is well known [6]. Based on that information, and the voltage dependence observed in Section III-A, we have an approximation for the LET by the secondary particles that are responsible for the SEB.

To investigate the deposited energy by the primary proton, we performed Monte Carlo simulations using the Geant4-based simulation toolkit G4SEE [26]. In the simulation model, the target dimensions were 1.8×2.8 mm with a $300\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ thickness of the SiC substrate where a $10\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ -thick SiC layer was defined as the sensitive volume (SV) at the top of the SiC layer. This thickness corresponds to the thickness of a fully depleted epitaxial layer in the SiC power devices used in this study. More details about the simulation model can be found in [20], where an identical model was used. A total of 1×10^7 primary protons were used in the simulations. From the simulated output, we include only the secondary particles with impact angles within 30° of normal incidence and with ranges over $5 \mu\text{m}$. Such criteria for SEB have been experimentally observed for similar devices [11], [27]. The criteria for the secondaries inducing SEB are illustrated in Fig. 5.

From these particles, the complementary cdf (CCDF, or *tail distribution*) for the LET values (in SiC) for each particle species is shown in Fig. 6. The heaviest secondary particle produced in our simulation, which satisfies our SEB criteria, is Al with 200-MeV primary proton energy. The maximum atomic number of the included secondaries increases with E_p . For $E_p = 53, 101,$ and 200 MeV, the heaviest secondaries are O, Na, and Al, respectively. All particles included in Fig. 6 are produced by inelastic processes. The range of particles from elastic processes in our simulation does not exceed $4 \mu\text{m}$ which means that they do not have sufficient range to induce SEB. This is in agreement with results from the work of Kuboyama et al. [17], where they conclude that instead of elastic reaction products, only spallation fragments and more specifically, Na and Al are responsible for SEB in SiC Schottky barrier diodes. Furthermore, they found that the produced secondary particle species do not depend on the primary proton energy between 30 and 70 MeV. At both proton energies, Na and Al were considered to be the secondary particle species responsible for SEB failures in their experiment.

Fig. 6. G4SEE-simulated complementary cumulative LET (in SiC) distribution per secondary ion species for different primary proton energies. The vertical axis indicates the probability per primary particle. Only those secondaries that meet our SEB criteria are included.

In our work, for 53-MeV primary protons, we consider O to be the heaviest particle responsible for SEB (see Fig. 6). The difference in the responsible particle species for initiating the burnout at similar proton energies is most likely due to the different technological constraints between the studies. The thickness of the active layer of the SiC Schottky barrier diode used in [17] is $3.7 \mu\text{m}$ and they report the ranges of the heaviest secondaries to be 3.5 and $4.3 \mu\text{m}$ for Al and Na, respectively. This means that many of the secondaries that are excluded from our LET spectra due to their short range ($< 5 \mu\text{m}$) can be responsible for SEB when the active layer thickness is smaller.

Regardless of particle species, the maximum LET value observed in the simulations tends to increase with increasing primary energy, which can be observed in Fig. 7, where all particle species are combined in one CCDF per primary proton energy. It also seems that at $\text{LET} < 4 \text{ MeV cm}^2 \text{ mg}^{-1}$, the 53-MeV primary protons produce more secondaries than the primary protons with higher energies. However, we assume that such low-LET particles do not contribute significantly to SEB at $V_{\text{DS}} = 1000$ V and below. This also aligns with the “hockey stick” SEB graph obtained with heavy ions,

Fig. 7. G4SEE-simulated complementary cumulative LET (in SiC) distribution of the secondary particles for different primary proton energies. Increasing primary proton energy E_p increases the count of high-LET secondary particles that meet our SEB criteria.

Fig. 8. Simulated Weibull plot for the secondary particles, which can induce SEB. The number of simulated protons was 1×10^7 . The horizontal axis represents the primary protons in the simulation scaled by their corresponding weight.

where the SEB threshold voltages increase rapidly with decreasing LET values below $10 \text{ MeV cm}^2 \text{ mg}^{-1}$ [6].

For the simulated secondary particles, we determine an LET threshold that would represent the minimum LET at which we assume an SEB to occur (see Fig. 7). By choosing an LET of $5 \text{ MeV cm}^2 \text{ mg}^{-1}$, we should be in the LET region where the SEB occurs but the voltage threshold is not saturated to $\sim 500 \text{ V}$. Such an LET value has been used as a criterion for SEB also in [6]. After setting this criterion for LET, we look at the secondary particle production along with the increasing number of primary particles in the simulation and perform a similar Weibull analysis as for the experimental data.

In the G4SEE simulated output data, there is a primary particle index (or *event index*) for each secondary particle and nuclear reaction. Therefore, we can link the production of the secondary particle with the primary proton. This allows us to sort the SEB-inducing secondary particles by their order of occurrence and present them in the Weibull scale (see Fig. 8). In addition, each event has a weight that indicates

the probability of the event to occur. To compare with the irradiation experiment, each event index of the secondary particles is scaled with its corresponding weight. This will represent the number of primary particles needed to produce each secondary particle that satisfies our criteria assumed to lead to a failure condition.

In the first assumption, all the particles that satisfy the criteria will induce an SEB. We apply our method by comparing the simulated data points with the experimental data in Fig. 1. In Fig. 8, we include the first ten valid secondary events for the sake of consistency with the experiment. When comparing the Weibull plots of the experiment (see Fig. 1) and the simulation (see Fig. 8), we see similar trends in both figures. The 200-MeV primary proton beam seems to be the worst case for SEB within the tested proton energies. This method can be used to determine the SV of SEB for SiC power devices. Furthermore, it can be used to assess the failure rates for applications in different radiation environments.

IV. CONCLUSION

The proton energy dependence of SEB cross section and leakage current degradation were studied. Experiments show that the increasing proton energy results in increasing SEB cross section as well as in increasing the probability for leakage current degradation. Based on Geant4 simulations, the higher energy primary proton interaction with the device material will produce more secondary particles which, due to their properties, are capable of causing device failure compared to those produced by lower proton energies. A method for linking the experimental results for SEB with Geant4 simulated secondary particle spectrum was presented. Such a method will help determine the failure criteria of particle radiation impact for SiC power devices and estimate failure rates in application environments.

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